

The Fifth Element: creating the divine science (DS)

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Abstract

In the formulas transformations the time, mass, length and force change depending on the speed of movement. Here we take a step further to unravel the relationship of time, mass, length and force. We will learn divine scheme based on circles and explore them using mathematical formulas. Our results will show that time and mass, length and force can be combined into time-mass and length-force tensors. Moreover, we will discover a surprising effect: the formulas transformations help us understand the structure of the eternity. By exploring different configurations of the equation, we will find that diffraction and interference is explained by a divine science. These results show a fundamental law of divine science and providing new understanding of being.

Introduction

There are four main elements – wind, earth, water, fire.

The Fifth Element activates the Elemental Stones that involves the four elements. Thus, time (t) is formed from wind, mass (m) from earth, length (x) from water, force (F) from fire.

And the Fifth Element forms the phase speed.

Crescents

Let's look at large circle equilateral triangle, formed from three points. The first point is the center of large circle, and two are the points of contact of the large circle and small circles. They contact large circle from top to bottom, or from bottom to top, or from right to left, or from left to right.

An equilateral triangle is surrounded by a small circles, where the diameter is a side of a triangle with length $\sqrt{2}$. And the side of the triangle equal to 1 is the radius of the large circle. The arcs of the small circles intersect with the large circle and form crescents.

Divine theorem

Let's consider how the lengths of the arcs in a crescent relate. Short arc equal to one quarter of the perimeter of a large circle $u_0 = \frac{1}{4}p_0$. A long arcequal to one-half the perimeter of a small circle $u = \frac{1}{2}p$.

Perimeter of the large circle $p_0 = 2\pi r \rightarrow u_0 = \frac{\pi r}{2}$, where r is the radius of the larger circle. And the perimeter of a small circle $p = \pi c \rightarrow u = \frac{\pi c}{2}$, where "c" is the diagonal smaller circle.

Here "c" is the diagonal side of a triangle, where the legs the sides are equal to "r" – the radius of the great circle. The diagonal is calculated by Pythagorean theorem:

$$r^2+r^2 = c^2$$

From the Pythagorean theorem it follows that $2r^2 = c^2$, and hence $c = \sqrt{2}r$.

For crescent the following theorem will be true:

$$u = \frac{u_0}{\sqrt{1-\frac{r^2}{c^2}}}, u > u_0$$

Proof:

$$\frac{u}{u_0} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\frac{r^2}{c^2}}} \rightarrow \frac{u}{u_0} = \sqrt{1-\frac{r^2}{c^2}}$$

$$\frac{u_0^2}{u^2} = 1 - \frac{r^2}{c^2} \rightarrow \frac{(\frac{\pi r}{2})^2}{(\frac{\pi c}{2})^2} = 1 - \frac{r^2}{c^2} \rightarrow \frac{r^2}{c^2} = 1 - \frac{r^2}{c^2}$$

$$\frac{r^2}{(\sqrt{2}r)^2} = 1 - \frac{r^2}{(\sqrt{2}r)^2} \rightarrow \frac{r^2}{2r^2} = 1 - \frac{r^2}{2r^2}$$

$$\frac{1}{2} = 1 - \frac{1}{2} \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{2}$$

The theorem is proven

Time and mass

The upper and lower sides of the large circle are in contact with two small circles, from which two crescents are formed. It has legs of a right triangle are the speed "v" and the diagonals "c" are phase speed. From this follow two physical formulas.

First formula: $t = \frac{t_0}{\sqrt{1-\frac{v^2}{c^2}}}, t > t_0$

Here “t” and “t₀” are times, and “v” is speed. Time lengthens when movement: the higher the speed, the longer the time becomes.

$$\text{Second formula: } m = \frac{m_0}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}, m > m_0$$

Here “m” and “m₀” are masses, and “v” is speed. Mass increases with movement: the higher the speed, the more the mass increases.

Length and force

The right-hand and left-hand sides of the large circle touch two small circles from which two crescents are formed. It has legs of a right triangle are the speed “v” and the diagonals

“c” are phase speed. From this follow two physical formulas.

$$\text{Third formula: } x = x_0 \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}, x < x_0$$

Here “x” and “x₀” are length, and “v” is speed. Length decreases when moving: the higher the speed, the smaller it becomes length.

$$\text{Fourth formula: } F = F_0 \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}, F < F_0$$

Here “F” and “F₀” are forces, and “v” is speed. Force decreases with movement: the greater the speed, the less force becomes.

Divine scheme

The divine scheme is formed from the connection of the schemes of time, mass, length and force.

The divine scheme shows the connection on the one side with time, mass, length, force, and on the other side with the speed of movement.

The divine scheme can be divided into two tensors – time-mass and force-length.

Tensor time-mass

The time-mass tensor can be represented as the formula $t^m = \begin{pmatrix} t & 0 \\ 0 & m \end{pmatrix}$.

Let's look at the scheme of the time-mass tensor.

We will see that there is also a zero time-mass tensor, which can be written as a formula.

$$t_{00}^m = \begin{pmatrix} t_0 & 0 \\ 0 & m_0 \end{pmatrix}$$

The time-mass tensor and the zero time-mass tensor are related by the formula.

$$t^m = \frac{t_{00}^m}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}, t^m > t_{00}^m$$

Tensor force-length

The force-length tensor can be represented as the formula $F^x = \begin{pmatrix} F & 0 \\ 0 & x \end{pmatrix}$.

Let's look at the scheme of the force-length tensor.

We will see that there is also a zero force-length tensor, which can be written as a formula.

$$F_{00}^x = \begin{pmatrix} F_0 & 0 \\ 0 & x_0 \end{pmatrix}$$

The force-length tensor and the zero force-length tensor are related by the formula.

$$F^x = F_{00}^x \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}, F^x < F_{00}^x$$

Divine formula

We see that the fourth formula $F = F_0 \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}$.
 And we see also that the third formula $x = x_0 \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}$. Therefore, we can equate these formulas.

$$\frac{F}{F_0} = \frac{x}{x_0} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}$$

From this equality we obtain the divine formula.

$$F x_0 = F_0 x$$

It is also the formula of leverage. This means that a smaller force F applied to a large length x_0 – a force lever – can move multiple force F_0 on a correspondingly smaller length x .

Eternity

Initial being, when it appeared, had the following dimensions – zero time t_0 , zero mass m_0 , zero length x_0 and zero force F_0 .

Modern being has the following dimensions – time t , mass m , length x and force F .

In the initial being the dimensions of length and force were greater than in the modern being.

$$x_0 > x, F_0 > F$$

And in the modern being the dimensions of time and mass are greater than in the initial being.

$$t > t_0, m > m_0$$

The Fifth Element is the speed of movement v .

And eternity consists of initial being, modern being and the Fifth Element.

Eternity has four great dimensions – t, m, x_0, F_0 . It also has four small dimensions – t_0, m_0, x, F . And it also includes the Fifth Element – v .

Divine law

Movement is driven by force and mass. Force and mass are determined by the divine law.

$$z = Fm$$

Here z – number, F – force, m – mass.

Diffraction

Force creates mass diffraction. Mass diffraction is a characteristic feature of matter propagation. Masses can fall into the region of geometric shadow – go around obstacles, penetrate through small holes in screens.

To understand why masses give a diffraction pattern according to the divine formula and law, consider the passage of a mass m through a slot of width x . In front of the slot, there is a screen on which a diffraction pattern with a width x_0 is formed.

This happens because the initial force F_0 , appearing according to divine law $z = Fm$, stretches the mass to width x_0 .

And the initial force F_0 is reduced to the value F according to the divine formula $Fx_0 = F_0x$.

Interference

Interference is a phenomenon in which two masses are combined by adding their masses or connection of masses taking into account their sizes.

The resulting mass may be more dense in places, or less dense than previous masses if the two masses increase in density or move apart, thereby decreasing the density.

Interference is also subject to divine law and formula. The initial force F_0 , appearing according to divine law $z = Fm$, stretches the mass to width x_0 .

And the initial force F_0 is reduced to the value F according to the divine formula $Fx_0 = F_0x$.

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